

titration was the same as described in earlier communication⁴. The representative pH titration curves is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Titration curves of AH.

TABLE I—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES WITH AH AND BH

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°, Dioxan-water = 3 : 1, μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

Constant	AH	BH
$pK_{LH_2}^H$	—	1.9
pK_{LH}^H	9.90	10.0
$\log K_{CuL}^{Cu}$	9.46	9.64
$\log K_{CuL_2}^{Cu}$	8.32	8.27
$\log K_{NiL}^{Ni}$	6.16	6.45
$\log K_{CoL}^{Co}$	6.08	5.97
$\log K_{ZnL}^{Zn}$	6.07	6.15
$\log K_{CdL}^{Cd}$	5.08	5.33
$\log K_{MgL}^{Mg}$	4.27	4.37

Limits of error ± 0.04 - 0.25.

Results and Discussion

Formation functions $\bar{n}_A$ (average number of H⁺ bound to ligand A⁻ or B⁻), $\bar{n}$ (average number of

ligand A⁻ or B⁻ bound to M(II) ions) and pL (where, [L] = equilibrium concentration of free ligand A⁻ and B⁻) were calculated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti using the pH titration curves⁵ (Fig. 1). The pK_{LH}^H and $pK_{LH_2}^H$ values of the ligands (LH₂ = AH₂ and BH₂) were evaluated by Bjerrum's half-integral method⁹. These values were further refined by the method of linear plots⁶. The formation curves of metal ligand systems were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ vs pL. The values of $\log K_{ML}^M$ and $\log K_{ML_2}^M$ were determined by half integral method and were further refined by the method of least-squares⁷. The results are stated in Table 1. The equilibrium constants K_{LH}^H corresponds to deprotonation of phenolic OH group of the ligands. Lower pK_{LH}^H value of AH is probably due to the steric effect.

The stability constants of complexes of bivalent metal ions with the ligands AH and BH are in good agreement with Irving-Williams order⁸.

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Evaluation of Excess Internal Pressure and Excess Free Length in Ternary Liquid Mixtures

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INTERACTION studies in binary liquid mixtures in the light of excess functions have been a matter of sufficient interest during the last few decades^{1,2}. The free length concept of Jacobson has been used by various workers to study the intermolecular interaction in binary liquid mixtures³. Kaulgud⁴ and Naidu and Krishnan⁵ have evaluated intermolecular free length employing thermodynamic approach, while Schaffs⁶ applied ultrasonic approach to evaluate intermolecular free length.

Internal pressure provides a severe and sensitive test⁷ for a theory of liquid state. Thermodynamic as well as ultrasonic measurements provide very accurate method for the evaluation of internal pressure^{8,9}. Pandey and Mishra¹⁰ extended the studies in binary liquid mixtures, where they evaluated the excess internal pressure, and showed that excess internal pressure like other excess thermodynamic properties, varies with change in composition and temperature in binary liquid mixtures. However, it appears from literature that evaluation of excess free length and excess internal pressure for ternary liquid mixture are rare.

In the present note, the theory for binary liquid mixture has been extended to ternary liquid mixture and excess internal pressure and excess free length have been evaluated for hexane—decane—hexadecane polymer homologues.

Theoretical : Several relations basically designed for binary liquid mixtures have been successfully extended for ternary liquid mixture by considering it to be made up of three binary mixtures and assuming that they are equivalent to single-component liquids^{11,12}. The molecules of the three components are divided into equal segments to that $V_1^* = V_2^* = V_3^* = V$. Assuming the additivity of the core volumes of the components and adopting the same procedure employed in the case of binary mixtures, it is possible to evaluate the parameters in the case of a ternary mixture.

Assuming the volume reduction parameter of the ternary mixture to be linear in mole fractions of the components we have¹¹

$$V^* = x_1 V_1^* + x_2 V_2^* + x_3 V_3^* \quad (1)$$

$$\text{and } V = \bar{V} (x_1 V_1^* + x_2 V_2^* + x_3 V_3^*) \quad (2)$$

where, V , V^* and $\bar{V}$ are molar, characteristic and reduced volume of the ternary mixture, respectively.

The expression for the internal pressure using Buchler's¹³ relation can be written as¹⁴

$$P_1 = \frac{2^{1/6} RT}{(2^{1/6} \bar{V} - d N^{1/3} V^{2/3})} \quad (3)$$

The rigid sphere diameter (d) of the molecule can be obtained from the following relation¹⁴,

$$d^{5/2} = \frac{1}{7.21 \times 10^{19}} \frac{V \cdot \sigma^{1/4}}{T_{c(m)}^{1/4}} \quad (4)$$

In equation (4), the critical temperature of the mixture has been obtained using the following relation,

$$T_{c(m)} = \sum_{i=1}^3 X_i T_{c_i} \quad (5)$$

The excess internal pressure is defined as difference between the internal pressure of the mixture $P_{i(m)}$ and that of an ideal mixture of the same composition which is given by the relation,

$$P_i^E = P_{i(m)} - \sum_{i=1}^3 X_i (P_i)_{id} \quad (6)$$

The intermolecular free length in liquids is defined as⁸

$$L_t = \frac{2V_a}{Y} \quad (7)$$

In equation (7), Y is the total surface area of the molecule and is given by

$$Y = (36\pi N V_a^2)^{1/3} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{and } V_a = V_i - V_o \quad (9)$$

where, V_a is available volume per mole and V_i is molar volume.

Substituting the value of V_a from equation (9) in equation (7) we get,

$$L_t = \frac{2(V_i - V_o)}{Y} \quad (10)$$

In case of ternary liquid mixture, equation (10) may be written as

$$L_{t(m)} = \frac{2[V_i - (x_1 V_{o1} + x_2 V_{o2} + x_3 V_{o3})]}{x_1 Y_1 + x_2 Y_2 + x_3 Y_3} \quad (11)$$

where, x_1 , x_2 , x_3 and Y_1 , Y_2 , Y_3 are mole fractions and available volume per mole of component 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

The molar volume at absolute zero (V_o) can be obtained from the relation,

$$V_o = V_i \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_o}\right)^{0.3} \quad (12)$$

The value of excess free length has been obtained from the relation,

$$L_t^E = L_{t(m)} - \sum_{i=1}^3 X_i L_{t_i} \quad (13)$$

Results and Discussion

The values of surface tension (σ), volume (V) and rigid sphere diameter (d) for ternary liquid mixture hexane (X_1), decane (X_2) and hexadecane (X_3) for the entire composition range are given in Table 1. The necessary data have been taken from literature^{12,13}. The calculated values of excess internal pressure (P_i^E) and excess free length (L_i^E) are listed in Table 1. Experimental value of excess internal pressure is also included in Table 1 for comparison. As is evident from the data, P_i^E and L_i^E values vary with the composition of the mixture, i.e. $P_i^E = P_i^E(X)$ and $L_i^E = L_i^E(X)$.

A perusal of Table 1 reveals that there is good agreement between theoretical and experimental values of excess internal pressure. These results show that there is interaction between the components of the mixture. The values of excess internal pressure which are indications for intermolecular interaction in the system studied, are negative except for $X_3 = 0.8580$ and 0.7532 . The values of L_i^E are negative for all mole fractions. The negative values of P_i^E and L_i^E increase with the

TABLE 1—SURFACE TENSION (σ), VOLUME (V), RIGID SPHERE DIAMETER (d), EXCESS INTERNAL PRESSURE (P_i^E) AND EXCESS FREE LENGTH (L_f^E) FOR THE MIXTURES OF HEXANE (X_1), DECANE (X_2) AND HEXADECANE (X_3) AT 303.15 K

x_1	x_2	σ dyne cm ⁻¹	V cm ³ mol ⁻¹	d Å	P_i^E K bar		L_f^E Å
					Theor.	Exptl.	
0.000 0	0.949 1	23.16	201.944	6.854 0	-0.029 7	-0.029 1	-0.002 8
0.000 0	0.825 6	23.82	214.098	7.022 2	-0.027 3	-0.046 5	-0.008 0
0.000 0	0.734 6	24.18	223.074	7.191 3	-0.026 3	-0.015 5	-0.010 2
0.000 0	0.598 8	24.79	236.429	7.310 2	-0.020 7	-0.019 9	-0.012 1
0.142 0	0.858 0	22.28	187.778	6.739 6	+0.075 2	-0.012 3	-0.010 3
0.142 0	0.753 2	22.44	198.104	6.791 5	+0.047 8	-0.021 7	-0.017 8
0.142 0	0.597 5	23.06	213.433	6.998 7	-0.045 1	-0.034 2	-0.025 2
0.142 0	0.446 7	23.24	228.279	7.178 1	-0.056 8	-0.043 7	-0.029 1
0.267 1	0.732 9	21.68	179.716	6.535 8	-0.025 6	-0.024 0	-0.017 6
0.267 1	0.635 3	21.84	182.337	6.667 6	-0.041 2	-0.028 8	-0.026 5
0.267 1	0.479 5	21.99	204.671	6.865 7	-0.063 1	-0.044 6	-0.036 9
0.267 1	0.390 2	22.16	213.464	6.972 2	-0.075 2	-0.052 7	-0.040 8
0.267 1	0.325 2	22.24	219.871	7.055 9	-0.075 1	-0.038 1	-0.042 7
0.503 1	0.496 9	20.44	164.517	6.300 3	-0.019 7	-0.020 8	-0.024 9
0.503 1	0.378 4	20.38	176.192	6.460 2	-0.053 6	-0.037 5	-0.041 2
0.503 1	0.305 8	20.33	183.338	6.554 0	-0.071 6	-0.047 4	-0.049 1
0.503 1	0.154 7	20.25	194.217	6.741 9	-0.102 1	-0.066 4	-0.061 7
0.503 1	0.098 0	20.27	203.807	6.811 6	-0.110 0	-0.073 0	-0.064 6
0.600 2	0.399 8	19.98	158.252	6.201 1	-0.013 2	-0.019 4	-0.025 1
0.600 2	0.276 1	19.80	170.437	6.361 3	-0.062 8	-0.037 9	-0.045 1
0.600 2	0.189 5	19.66	178.976	6.479 3	-0.081 6	-0.050 3	-0.055 8
0.600 2	0.119 0	19.53	185.921	6.586 1	-0.101 0	-0.060 1	-0.063 1
0.600 2	0.069 8	19.35	190.761	6.622 6	-0.115 8	-0.066 7	-0.067 7

decrease in mole fraction of decane and the increase in mole fraction of hexane.

Hence, from the above discussion, it may be concluded that the theory employed to evaluate excess internal pressure and excess free length for binary liquid mixtures may be successfully extended to ternary liquid mixtures, and P_i^E and L_f^E , like binary liquid mixtures, vary with composition of the mixture in ternary liquid mixture.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Spiro-[2-isoxazoline-4,2'-(1'H)-naphthalen-1-ones]

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NAPHTHISOXAZOLES are known to exhibit a wide spectrum of physiological properties like analgesic, antipyretic and antiinflammatory activities¹. Recently, the compounds have been reported to possess high antimicrobial activity². The present investigation was taken up with a view to synthesise new derivatives and to screen them for their antimicrobial activity.

2-Benzal-1-tetralones³ obtained by the base-catalysed condensation of 1-tetralone with various aromatic aldehydes have been treated with benzoni-trile oxide in refluxing ether. The nitrile oxide has been generated *in situ* by the action of triethylamine on benzhydroxamoyl chloride⁴. The cyclised